

Aesop project: a new architectural approach to change management.

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Abstract. Despite their wide variability in constitution and operation, Chambers of Commerce all share a responsibility to develop and deliver complex and often specialised services for their members. The enterprises for whom these services are designed have needs which are also complex, requiring a combination of services from various sources delivered in a coordinated way.

Matching needs and offers introduces a third complexity: intermediation and brokerage. This paper introduces the work of the Aesop project which is exploring the concept of a third generation portal which supports service provision and intermediation relationships in economic development and business support networks. It aims to take familiar concepts, such as catalogue and case management, decision support and transaction coordination, and to deliver them in highly distributed and reconfigurable ways to match the variety of social, political and commercial contexts in which the Chambers of Commerce of Europe as called on to operate.

We present scenarios drawn from Emilia-Romagna, Rhone Alpes and Stuttgart to show how a common model of intermediation roles and relationships can be reconfigured to represent local concerns and practises and provide an outline definition of the set of portal capabilities and resources required to address these divers requirements.

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1. Introduction

The AESOP project commenced in 2002 and in the completion of its first phase has identified a common model for Third Generation Portal services which will provide a managed and secure on line “workspace” between the Chambers and their members. In fact, while much progress has been achieved in giving on-line access to data and services there is much to understand and to be achieved to the deliver the ability to work on-line in an effective way. In such a direction AESOP aims to deliver three main results:

- an action research result - Co-ordinated by the University of Newcastle upon Tyne, ARDEMI of Lyon, Fraunhofer IAO of Stuttgart and Unioncamere of Bologna will undertake and publish a set of ethnographically informed studies into impact and change management issues of technology development. These will be expressed in both observation and analysis and in the publication of a coherent common architectural approach to the support of relationship management;
- a technical result – T-Systems MMS Dresden will develop flexible Portal

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Management Systems with easy configurable components for the efficient delivery of on-line Chamber of Commerce services,

- an implementation and use result - using the common technical platform three regional Chambers of Commerce (Rhone Alpes, Stuttgart and Emilia-Romagna) will validate the model and enhance their organisations and services.

Starting from a description of the situation of the Chambers in Europe, this paper describes how a common brokerage model can be designed from the activities of three different Chambers of commerce and a basic technical infrastructure can deliver the functionalities needed to support the model itself.

2. Chambers of commerce in Europe.

According to Eurochambres² membership records there are more than 1,500 Chambers of Commerce in 36 European countries, representing about 15,000,000 enterprises. Each Chamber of Commerce differs outwardly from others by name, size, offered services, number of members etc. all of which can be connected to the local environment the Chamber is working in. Amongst the Chambers different models and potential groups can be identified, but a widely recognized distinction exists between public law and private law systems. Chambers in a public law system are regulated by a national law usually defining the Chambers as part of the public administration sector, whereas chambers in a private law system are organisations run basically as private associations.

2.1 A map of European systems.

In the European Union area Austrian, German, Spanish, French, Greek, Italian, Luxembourg and Dutch Chambers are public law systems, while Belgian, Danish, Irish, Finnish, British, Portuguese and Swedish are private law systems.

Chambers in the EU are regulated mostly by Ministries or bodies equally competent who oversee the national systems.

The Eastern and Central European Chamber system is mainly laid down to a private law system (Bulgaria, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania) and for a few of them to a public dependency (Croatia, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Slovenia).

Whereas the above mentioned dichotomy in the EU area influences the existence of an overseeing body, in the Eastern and Central Europe, management of the entire system is not empowered to anyone, except for Hungary.

Finally an upside down situation is in the MEDA Region, where public law system Chambers are double of the others (Algeria, Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, Palestine, Tunisia and Turkey for the public – Cyprus, Israel, Malta, Syria for the private). Basically same UE situation in respect of bodies watching over the system.

2.2 Differences in roles and dimensions.

Chambers who work under a public law system have usually a large number of members³, due to a compulsory registration while membership in private law systems is voluntary. The

² Eurochambres, the European Association of Chambers of Commerce and Industry, keeps records of the main European Chambers activity, grouping them in geographical areas. In particular Eurochambres focus on the EU, Eastern and Central Europe and MEDA Region.

³ The main systems in this group are: Italy with 5 mln companies, Germany with 3 mln, Spain with 2 mln, and France with 1.8 mln.

different registration systems lead to different dimensions and roles.

All chambers playing in a public law system characterize themselves for a bigger size and a deeper involvement (and considerable importance) in relationships with public authorities and regional governments making this group fundamentally different from the smaller private law Chambers, that are called to a merely consultative role before public authorities and regions.

2.3 Main common activities and services.

Compulsory membership greatly contribute to the chamber finance along with fee for administrative certificates, sale of services and sometimes state contributions; very often Chambers carry out public functions, such as management of national business registers, vocational training and infrastructures (ports, airports, roads).

Private law chambers are self supporting bodies, and raise funds by voluntary subscriptions and sale of services, including from issue of trade certificates, training services, arbitration, conciliation to participation in international projects.

But, despite the differences previously outlined Chambers of commerce uphold two basic functions, with no distinction of area or system wherever they operate:

- a common duty in representing general interest of companies;
- a common orientation in providing information and/or information-based services (advice, promotion, training, internationalisation, arbitration and conciliation).

Briefly, all the Chambers are information brokers.

3. Three different scenarios.

Three major regional Chambers of Commerce, Rhone-Alpes (F), Stuttgart (DE) and Emilia-Romagna (I) are the three chambers where the brokerage activity has been analysed and a common architectural model has been designed during the Aesop project. Each Chamber has a strong background in use of ICT and a commitment to the effective deployment of ICT to improve the quality and efficiency of services offered to the members.

3.1 Emilia-Romagna: customised economic and market information.

The Chamber of Commerce serves a wide number of SMEs and institutions (e.g. training centres, local government authorities and private consultants etc) with basic statistical information (data tables about import-export, industrial sectors, financial data etc.), general reports about the regional economy (short range forecasts, industrial production, GDP estimates) and ad hoc reports and tailored analyses on-demand about market conditions, locally and abroad. The establishment of a virtual environment to perform the explorative steps with the client on-line, presenting possible solutions with the co-operation of the customers and with the co-operation of the different people working in the regional association and/or in the network of the chambers is perceived like a mean to increase quality and flexibility of the work inside Chambers departments.

3.2 Rhone-Alpes access to network of expert services and information to assist innovation and technology transfer to SMEs:

In the Rhone Alpes Regional Chamber of Commerce one of the high priorities is to encourage the development of SMEs by promoting technology transfer and innovation. The Regional Chamber provides expert services to 8 district offices. The goal of the

brokerage activity is to offer technology transfer services to SMEs of the region and to help them to develop their innovative products/services. The establishment of a managed on line workspace will offer the capability of brokering a technology transfer collaboration between different SMEs.

3.3 Stuttgart: secure procedures in vocational training.

The Stuttgart Chamber of Commerce is developing an overall strategy to introduce secure digital signature procedures for Members to access a range of Chamber services.

To over 60 centres within its own area the Chamber provides vocational training services for apprentices employed by its member companies. There are two examinations per year leading to the award of the apprenticeship certificates: practical in company training and theoretical training in vocational schools. The Chamber will provide a secure on-line workspace where to make available to accredited training centre examination papers, evaluation standards, results, certificates, etc.

3.4 Economic information, technology transfer and vocational training: what's common?

Each of the Chamber of Commerce acts as an intermediary and information broker and shares one or more of the following characteristics:

- a number of different interests are represented which may have elements of competition as well as co-operation. There is a complex interaction between collective and individual benefits for the participants.
- The business models and the patterns of commercial relationships are expected to evolve. Initial levels of trust and mutuality may change with experience and the solution must be able to adapt to and even promote these emergent changes.
- The boundaries of the applications environments are expected to be relatively fluid with the potential for a high inflow of new sources and clients and a high degree of mobility of brokerage relationships. Providers will be exploring new ways of combining and aggregating while clients will be taking increasing responsibility for the co-ordination of the service sets which are delivered to them.

With different goals, with different way to express their needings and projects, all the Chambers environments are suitable to be described in terms of a common model.

4. A common brokerage model

We can briefly describe the brokerage model⁴ in terms of roles and responsibility that different subjects (the customer, the broker and the information suppliers) assume in an information oriented activity such as those analysed in the different Chambers of commerce.

Figure n.1 depicts the different roles customers and brokers usually play in their relationships:

- searching for solutions, taking decisions, committing and evaluating the information obtained are typical roles of the clients;
- the broker takes care of offer formation (offers of service are selected, registered and organised), of rendezvous (publicity and dissemination of the information produced by

⁴ The initial versions of this model were developed in the ACTS project COBRA. A full description of this model requires an agreement on terms and definition clearly exceeding the limits of this paper. For more refer to [1].

different suppliers, bridging and translating the different languages of clients and suppliers, provider publication and client search, selection and application), of managing transactions and facilitating the evaluation process (evaluation and post-transaction responsibilities).

figure 1: Roles and relationships in information brokerage.

We can also insert in the customer and broker spaces the different instruments used to support and mediate the relationships (figure 2): market offers, register of offers, evaluation reports, classified information catalogues and advertisements are common communication and working tools.

figure 2: An instrumental view of the model.

What is worth noting is that in different situations these spaces of roles, relationships and instruments can be crossed in different ways, starting from different access point and with different scopes:

- in incremental product or service evolution, suppliers interpret previous demand in order to formulate new market offers. These must be registered, classified and advertised within a catalogue environment before any transaction can take place. This often happens for the Emilia-Romagna chamber's activity as well as that of Stuttgart's;
- in innovation led development, suppliers offer new and possibly unfamiliar products or services; interpretation by potential customers, stimulates a latent need and demand. Such developments may require the definition of new categories and classifications, as in the Rhone Alpes technology transfer activity;
- in market led product development, customers may generate a demand for new products or services which are not yet available. Suppliers respond with new offers, and the Chambers often classify, mediate and support the new offers in testing phases.

While scopes and directions are changing, the model and the basic functions to be supported can be clearly identified and embedded in a system.

5. Supporting brokerage: from structures to infrastructures.

5.1 From structures to infrastructures

From the architectural work in the initial phase of the project clearly demonstrated that the common model can not be supported by a fixed process, as is usually the case in a workflow application forcing users to follow one of the potential paths to traverse the brokerage space. It is better supported by set of infrastructural elements, that can be made general and reusable. The following list represents the current consensus among Chambers and their technical providers:

- *Secured shared space server* to provide a user managed and secure on line "workspace" between the Chambers and their members, a space where to "close the door" within networks and systems so that users can have a private exchange in a private space. This is something that users are not able to do dynamically and autonomously in current systems and appears to be *the most relevant and innovative infrastructure to be provided to users*: systems security is not usually considered something to leave under users control.
- *Case Management* in which the identities and other information about clients, the records of past interactions, current activities and plans are maintained and are linked to all the resources required to deliver service to that client. In the proposed approach, maintaining records will be a side effect of delivering service rather than an administrative overhead.
- *Decision Support* Chambers are constantly acquiring information and experience about the nature of information needs, the resources which are available to meet those needs and the processes of delivery. This knowledge is embedded in a number of communities of practice and networks of relationships.
- *Catalogue Management* in which all the information about what is available is organised and maintained. In the context of the market information service, it is no use just delivering the requested information but that other services need to be configured to make the information useful to the client. Thus, the catalogue must be seen not only as a means of discovering, selecting and delivering services but also as a tool for

constructing complex service packages and for maintaining and sharing information about the utility and effectiveness of the offers.

Integration of services into a portal system on different levels (view, process, model, persistence level) and with the aid of different protocols (e.g. IIOP or SOAP) will provide a coherent way for the users to access and reconfigure them when changes in the environment (new ways of traversing the brokerage model spaces) will appear. The integration will also provide usual modular functions to the users (e.g. workflow management, transaction management, user profiling, ...).

Defining the 3rd generation portal

There are many different ways to make sense of the evolution of the components of distributed systems and to classify approaches. We are not particularly concerned with any single categorisation and offer the following as a working model for the purposes of our project:

1st Generation: This sort of portal overcame the limitations of the client-server view of distribution. As long as systems conformed to the client-server model, there was no possibility for intermediation and brokerage. 1st generation portals connected to a number of “servers” collecting, organising and synthesising content and offering this, value-adding intermediation service to its clients. These portals are neither a clients or a servers.

2nd Generation: This sort of system added transactions and business logic to the 1st generation capabilities. Now a business process could be mapped onto a network of such portals allowing complex value chains, markets and communities to be mediated. It is a characteristic of these portals, however, that the process of defining the business processes and configuring the workflows is situated in a different domain from that of use. What is delivered to the user is a predefined application albeit with some capability for dynamic reconfiguration.

3rd Generation: This sort of portal removes this restriction. It offers access to distributed resources, relating to content, communication and transaction, and underlying computational resources in a form where they can be appropriated, configured and exploited in ways that are defined *by the users, through their use*.

6. Conclusions

All Chambers are different: they operate in different business, cultural and legal contexts, they all do different things and everything they do, they do it differently.

In the first phase of the Aesop project we have focussed on trying to analyse these assertions discovering important issues for both the suppliers of applications and infrastructure and to smart organisations in their role as procurers and users of such systems. Our most important observations and conclusions at this stage are:

1. As long as the focus remains at the applications level and on what the Chambers, and the people who work in them, *do*, then there is little agreement about common interests and systems: at this level, everyone is, indeed, unique. The way we usually approach requirements capture, and provide input to applications designers and implementers, tends to force us to remain precisely at this level: this is a problem.
2. There are, however, very significant opportunities to define systems which have wide interest. But to identify them, we need to shift our attention from the daily practices to more abstract models, from the applications level to the infrastructure level.
3. By making this shift we have had been able to provide a practical example of how

initial discussions about requirements and interests in three distinct Chambers can be transformed from a picture of diversity and uniqueness to a common model, supported by new elements of infrastructure of high common interest.

This gives us some strong indicators regarding the nature and functions of a 3rd generation portal: a set of infrastructures supporting the development of secured social spaces, preserving memory and facilitating relationships, easily reconfigurable as so on as roles, rules and relationships change.

7. References

[1] Aesop web site at <http://www.aesop-ist.com/>